

TransformAr

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in
Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation
packages

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adaptation**
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This guidance document is based on the following three outputs:

- The MIP4Adapt Transformational Adaptation Thematic Working Group Policy Brief “Understanding Transformational Adaptation: A shared vision across EU Horizon projects”
- An academic paper titled “Defining and assessing Transformational Adaptation: the TransformAr Scorecard” submitted to Environmental Research Communications
- An online webtool scorecard.transformar.eu

The EU is ambitious in its climate goals, with the objective to become climate resilient by 2030. This means that we need to speed up, and do more, but how? The TWG TA Policy Brief introduces the concept of transformational adaptation, based on the IPCC’s 6th Assessment Report. The policy brief emphasizes that transformational adaptation is a strategic, systemic approach focused on addressing the root causes of vulnerability to climate change. Instead of short-term, incremental responses, transformational adaptation seeks fundamental shifts in economic, governance, and social systems, ensuring long-term climate resilience. It also highlights that transformational adaptation should be proactive, considering future uncertainties and aiming to reduce harm to people, socio-economic systems, and natural environments. Moreover, it identifies barriers to transformational adaptation related to: incentives, conflicting interests (e.g., economic growth versus nature conservation), costs and uncertainty induced by the required long-term vision.

While the policy brief gives example case studies of transformational adaptation and gives some recommendations for putting transformational adaptation into practice, the academic paper and the scorecard work towards assessing the transformational potential of adaptation solutions or projects. Five principles of transformational adaptation are identified: scope, impact areas, depth, temporality, and inclusivity. These principles are split into more concrete criteria. Both principles and the corresponding criteria were derived from a literature review on transformational adaptation (e.g., Chhetri et al., 2019; Deubelli and Mechler, 2021; Fedele et al., 2019; Kasdan et al., 2021; Scolobig et al., 2023). The criteria were translated into statements, easily answerable by project stakeholders and finally implemented into an online webtool.

The TransformAr Scorecard is a self-assessment tool for developers or stakeholders of adaptation programs or projects to assess to what extent their project is transformational. The goal is to identify whether the adaptation project can improve on certain criteria to create more long-term, systemic and impactful (transformational) change. The tool’s results dashboard allows respondents to identify the strengths and weaknesses of their adaptation project from a transformational adaptation point of view. For example, if a project scores poorly on the criterion ‘equitable’, then project developers know that they should improve the consideration or involvement of vulnerable citizens (e.g., elderly, economically disadvantaged citizens). If a project scores highly on the criterion ‘scalability’, the project developers know that their efforts to make the project replicable contribute to the project’s transformational character. The assessment can be done before, during, or after implementing an adaptation project, but is ideally done ex ante, when improvements can still be made.

This deliverable integrates the efforts of many contributors, also beyond TransformAr. Firstly, a lot of gratitude goes towards all co-authors of the policy brief, members of the Thematic Working Group on Transformational Adaptation. Secondly, thank you to Guido Schmidt and Teresa Geidel from Fresh Thoughts Consulting for contributing to the academic paper and the Scorecard. Finally, a big thank you goes to Carla Garcia-Lozano (University of Girona), Pål Godard (Gjøvik), Efren Feliu Torres (Tecnalia), Amaya Soto (CETMAR) and Bert Voortman (Rijkswaterstaat) for validating the scorecard through an interview about their adaptation solutions.

INTRODUCTION

Climate change presents a challenge to societies worldwide, as it exacerbates existing vulnerabilities and introduces new risks to human and ecological systems. Raising temperatures will exacerbate the heat island effect in urban areas, and deteriorate the health and liveability of its residents (Leal Filho et al., 2022). Severe precipitation in combination with insufficient drainage, especially in urbanised areas, makes communities susceptible to flooding. This increasing frequency and intensity of extreme weather events necessitates urgent and effective adaptation strategies to mitigate these impacts (Deubelli & Mechler, 2021; Kates et al., 2012; Warner et al., 2019).

While coping responses and incremental adaptation efforts have been the traditional response, they are proving insufficient in the face of severe climate disruptions. This inadequacy highlights the need for transformational adaptation, which involves fundamental changes in systems and practices to address the root causes of vulnerability through more comprehensive and long-term measures which consider both current and future climate risks alongside with their root causes (Fedele et al., 2019; Kates et al., 2012; Vermeulen et al., 2018). These fundamental changes adjust social-ecological relationships and cause the system to move toward a more resilient state (Barnes et al., 2020; Deubelli & Mechler, 2021).

Defining transformational adaptation is crucial for guiding policy and practice, as it provides a framework for understanding what is required to achieve sustainable adaptation outcomes (Deubelli & Mechler, 2021; Kasdan et al., 2021; Ulibarri et al., 2022). However, there is no single definition of transformational adaptation (Kasdan et al., 2021). The IPCC defines transformational adaptation, in their Sixth Assessment Report (AR6), as “actions aiming at adapting to climate change resulting in significant changes in structure or function that go beyond adjusting existing practices” (Nalau et al., 2023). Moreover, these adaptations “can be adopted at a large scale, can lead to new strategies in a region or resource system, transform places and potentially shift locations” and lead to “deep and long-term societal changes that influence sustainable development (including values, worldviews)”. The EU Policy Brief “Understanding Transformational Adaptation” (Cools et al., 2024), which this study is based on, builds on this IPCC definition. The policy brief provides a shared vision across EU Horizon projects and is developed under the Working Group on Transformational Adaptation of the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change's Implementation Platform (MIP4Adapt). It specifies characteristics of and barriers of transformational adaptation and provides numerous examples of transformational adaptation, covering a broad range of domains. The scorecard aims to close, what Deubelli and Mechler (2021) call, the ‘operationalisation gap’. There is an ambition for transformational change, visible from the vast academic and grey literature (policy documents, etc.), which is not met with practical implementation of transformative strategies. Insights into the operational criteria which make up transformational adaptation allow policymakers and practitioners to develop recommendations for planning and implementing transformational adaptation. This involves integrating transformational strategies into risk management, expanding the range of innovative adaptation options, and ensuring that adaptation efforts are inclusive and equitable (Fedele et al., 2019; Kates et al., 2012; Ulibarri et al., 2022). Moreover, by defining and understanding the principles and criteria of transformational adaptation, stakeholders themselves can make informed decisions that lead to effective and sustainable adaptation strategies.

This scorecard is intended for self-assessment by project developers or stakeholders with knowledge on the project's design, planning and implementation processes. The scorecard is developed using the transformational adaptation principles and criteria identified in literature and consolidated in a set of characteristics described in the EU Policy Brief on Transformational Adaptation (Cools et al., 2024). In the scorecard, the characteristics of Transformational Adaptation are translated into concrete and easily understandable statements, referred to as ‘indicators’. After filling in the scorecard, respondents receive a results dashboard which provides scores for each of the criteria. This helps stakeholders identify areas of improvement or the solution's strengths from a transformational adaptation point of view. The tool

can be used ex ante or ex post. An ex ante assessment is useful when there is still room to improve or intervene (but eventually some information required by the scorecard may not yet be available). In an ex post assessment, the transformational potential of an adaptation solution which has already been implemented (at the pilot or demonstrator level) is evaluated.

In what follows, we first go more into depth on the definition of transformational adaptation, why it is needed and the barriers to transformational adaptation. Then, we describe the principles and criteria which make up transformational adaptation followed by an explanation of the TransformAr Scorecard. This is followed by two case studies to demonstrate the use of the scorecard (one demonstrator of the TransformAr project and another from IMPETUS, another EU Horizon project on climate adaptation). Finally, we discuss the scorecards limitations and complementary tools.

Defining transformational adaptation

1.1 What is climate adaptation?

Climate adaptation refers to the process of 'process of adjusting to actual or expected climate and its effects' (IPCC, 2014). In human systems, adaptation aims to reduce harm or leverage beneficial opportunities brought about by these changes. For instance, it may involve modifying agricultural practices to cope with altered weather patterns or upgrading infrastructure to withstand extreme weather events. In some natural systems, human interventions may also play a role in facilitating adaptation (IPCC, 2014). More broadly, adaptation is understood as adjustments in both natural and human systems in response to climatic stimuli, helping to moderate damage or exploit potential advantages (IPCC, 2007; as cited in Termeer et al., 2017).

At the policy level, the European Union is actively working on climate adaptation through initiatives like the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change. This mission seeks to support at least 150 European regions and communities in becoming climate-resilient by 2030. It emphasizes collaborative, locally tailored solutions that help communities prepare for and reduce the impacts of climate-related risks, such as floods, droughts, and heatwaves.

1.2 Incremental versus transformational adaptation

Incremental adaptation refers to small-scale adjustments made within existing systems to maintain their functionality in the face of climate change. It focuses on accommodating changes by making minor modifications to current social-ecological systems, aiming to enhance their resilience while preserving the core structure and processes of these systems (Adger & Jordan, 2009; Kates et al., 2012). These strategies are often anticipatory, addressing immediate climate-related risks and development needs through short-term measures. For instance, improving irrigation systems to cope with altered rainfall patterns or strengthening infrastructure to withstand extreme weather events are examples of incremental adaptation (Fedele et al., 2019; Nalau et al., 2023). This approach emphasizes maintaining the "essence and integrity" of systems, keeping them within their current state or scale (Nalau et al., 2023).

In contrast, transformational adaptation entails more profound changes that alter the fundamental attributes of systems to better respond to the long-term impacts of climate change (Watkiss & Cimato, 2020). Instead of focusing on preserving the status quo, transformational adaptation envisions new pathways for development, addressing underlying vulnerabilities and inequalities while preparing for future uncertainties (Chu et al., 2019). It requires shifts across systems rather than within them, such as relocating entire communities from high-risk coastal areas or transitioning to sustainable energy systems. These changes aim for more open-ended outcomes and involve planned management, often necessitating a radical shift in practices and governance (Lonsdale et al., 2015).

While incremental adaptation focuses on adjusting existing practices to suit changing conditions, transformational adaptation looks at doing entirely different things, reshaping both natural and human systems in the face of evolving climate realities (Watkiss & Cimato, 2020). Both approaches play crucial roles in climate resilience, but transformational adaptation becomes increasingly necessary as climate change accelerates, threatening the limits of incremental measures.

The aforementioned policy brief compares incremental and transformational adaptation using Figure 1 as an illustration. Incremental adaptation here consists of implementing one measure at a time (the blue blocks) focusing on mitigating immediate climate risks, whereas transformational adaptation consists of a whole-of-society approach, leaving no-one behind and considering other sustainability dimensions besides climate action.

Figure 1: Incremental versus transformational adaptation, from Cools et al. (2024)

1.3 Why is transformational adaptation necessary?

Transformational adaptation is necessary to address the complex and often unprecedented climate challenges for several key reasons. Firstly, climate change impacts, such as sea-level rise, extreme weather events, and shifting ecosystems, are expected to be severe and long-lasting (IPCC, 2021). Incremental changes may not be adequate to cope with the magnitude and speed of these changes, necessitating a more radical overhaul of systems. Where previously incremental steps sufficed, these may no longer be effective under larger changes in climate. For example, increasing irrigation frequency and volumes in agriculture is not sufficient when a region is continuously suffering from droughts. In that case, a transformation towards different crops or even relocation may be necessary.

Transformational adaptation has the potential to create systems which are resilient to a wide range of climate impacts, but also other risks. The Netherlands' Delta Works, for example, is a large system of dams and dikes originally designed as a flood defence system. Through its integration with renewable energy infrastructure (hydropower and windfarms), this project has also reduced the country's dependence on fossil fuels, enhancing their energy security.

In the long run, transformational adaptation can be more cost-effective. While it may require significant investment, it can reduce the damage caused by extreme weather events and therefore the financial resources needed for emergency response and recovery. Certain transformational changes may have other monetary benefits arising from increased (mental) health, appreciation of real estate, the creation of employment opportunities, etc. With incremental solutions, the focus is more on the short run, not considering such future benefits.

1.4 Barriers to transformational adaptation

It is generally agreed that few real-life examples exist on transformational adaptation (O'Neill et al., 2022, Kuhl et al., 2021). Most adaptations remain incremental stepwise changes. Many barriers can hinder the success of transformational adaptation.

A first barrier is the involvement and consideration of many actors (stakeholders, sectors, governance levels, etc.) with different interests (Fedele et al. 2019). It is difficult to reconcile different future visions within a change project, e.g. economic growth versus nature preservation and scaling down economic activities. Powerful actors who benefit from the status quo have the potential to prohibit drastic change due to inequalities between the involved players (Fedele et al. 2019). Relatedly, an underestimated barrier is institutional organisation or complexity. The procedures to steer and implement transformational adaptation can be heavy and unclear. Examples are the implementation of a nature-based solution by multiple organisations. The pooling of financial resources or permitting systems can be unprecedented. The land ownership and tenure may require legal steps, and social conflicts may halt the implementation process (Vojinovic, 2020, Hernández-Mora and De Stefano, 2018).

A second barrier to transformational adaptation is financial barriers. A transformational adaptation may require high investments in terms of human capital, financial resources and time (Fedele et al. 2019, Kates et al. 2012). This is a particularly high barrier for the poorest communities, which are likely most vulnerable to climate change and at the same time do not have the resources to initiate transformational adaptation (Matyas and Pelling 2015). Moreover, the future benefits of new adaptations may be uncertain (Kates et al. 2012). Because transformational adaptation implies a change in direction, there may also be unexpected secondary costs which arise from a new system state (Matyas and Pelling 2015). Transformational adaptation may jeopardise the stability of economies, ecosystems, or societies (Matyas and Pelling 2015).

A third barrier is lack of knowledge. There is uncertainty in people's vulnerabilities to climate change the future occurrence of extreme weather events, in particular (Kates et al. 2012). Moreover, there is a gap between climate change knowledge and meaningful action (Lonsdale et al. 2015). Steering transformational change requires a specific personality and skillset as well as a high level of reflection (Lonsdale et al. 2015).

A fourth barrier is human mindset and behaviour (Kates et al. 2012). Humans generally like certainty and maintaining the status quo (Lonsdale et al. 2015). Incremental adaptation does not challenge this status quo and allows the future to be predictable and controllable (Fedele et al. 2019, Lonsdale et al. 2015). Transformational adaptation requires a far-reaching vision because it takes a long time for the benefits to become visible (Fedele et al. 2019). Humans generally prioritise near-term benefits. Moreover, people typically respond to visible risks while climate impacts tend to be less visible (Lonsdale et al. 2015). In order to integrate transformational adaptation into a vision of the future, it requires strategies for framing it as attractive and desirable.

Principles, criteria and indicators of transformational adaptation

For the development of an assessment tool to evaluate transformational adaptation we look towards *principles, criteria and indicators* (PC&I), an approach often used for sustainability assessments (Van Cauwenbergh et al., 2007). This approach, firstly, relies on the identification of principles or premises that define, or the general conditions needed to achieve transformational adaptation. Because the literature, both academic and grey literature, on transformational adaptation is extensive, we do this through a review of the literature. Alternatively, participatory methods such expert consultation could be used (e.g.

Delphi study for achieving consensus). This approach is much more labour and time-intensive, hence only preferred when documentation on the topic is limited. In a second step, these basic principles were translated into criteria for the assessment of the transformational character of projects. These criteria were also derived from the literature examined. Such criteria are more specific and easier to assess than principles. They express concrete requirements to evaluate whether an adaptation project is in line with each of the principles or not (Bautista et al., 2016). Finally, criteria have been detailed in indicators, or qualitative or quantitative expressions which allow for assessing performance against the criteria. In what follows, we firstly describe the principles and criteria derived from literature. In the next section, we explain the translation of these criteria into measurable indicators and the development of the TransformAr Scorecard.

Based on a review of the literature on transformational adaptation, we arrive at the five general principles listed below. Each of these principles gives rise to several criteria. A schematic overview of the principles and criteria is provided in Figure 2.

1. **Scope:** the adaptation solution should influence a large geographic area or sector or a large number of stakeholders, with potential spillovers in terms of weather risk reduction to other areas, communities or sectors.
2. **Impacts areas:** the adaptation solution should have an impact on the public's beliefs and attitudes towards climate change and adaptation and the governance structures and modes of cooperation.
3. **Depth:** the adaptation solution should change the core of the system (e.g., its economic focus) and/or its processes, i.e., the 'before' state should significantly differ from the 'after' state.
4. **Temporality:** the adaptation solution should have a long-term perspective, be non-reversible, generate future benefits and be flexibly adjustable to future (climatic) changes.
5. **Inclusivity:** the adaptation solution should consider other sustainability factors (such as non-discrimination, environment conservation, climate mitigation) besides climate adaptation.

The principle 'scope' consists of three different criteria. Some sources claim that transformational adaptation occurs at a large scale, either in terms of geographical area or the number of people affected (Kasdan et al., 2021). Others suggest that transformational approaches can occur at 'any level, from the individual through to the collective, industry or region' (Park et al., 2012, p. 199). We refer to the first criterion as 'systemwide', meaning that the adaptation solution affects an entire region, sector, ecosystem or community, rather than a single component of a system (Fedele et al., 2019; Kates et al., 2012; Scolobig et al., 2023). It is therefore more important to have a comprehensive approach, rather than operating at a very large scale. An important remark here is that there is no single definition of 'the system' as this is dependent on the context or location. The second criterion 'multiscale' means that the adaptation solution influences other systems or contexts besides the one which is directly being targeted (Deubelli & Mechler, 2021). In other words, the effects spill over from one geographic area to a neighbouring one, or from one sector to another. Switching from arable farming to agroforestry, for example, could be considered an adaptation measure for farmers affected by climate change (Fedele et al., 2019). This conversion may also result in improved water quality for the non-farming community, a different stakeholder group. This criterion also refers to the involvement of actors at multiple scales and levels of government, i.e., local, regional and national (Barnes et al., 2020). Multi-scale can also refer to a pooling of financial resources from multiple channels. Adaptation solutions may start off from a publicly funded pilot project, but should be supplemented by local government, private or community-based funding sources to ensure longevity, for example (Chu et al., 2019). If the adaptation solution itself is not implemented at a large scale—because it is in a pilot or demonstrator phase, for example—its scope may

be increased in the future. This third criterion is referred to as ‘scalable’¹. This may mean either that the system size is increased (e.g., the geographic area is made larger, the sector is broadened) or that the solution is replicated or reproduced elsewhere. This scalability should already be considered during the project planning phase. A condition for receiving funding from the UNFCCC Green Climate Fund, for example, is the project’s paradigm shift potential which is defined as the “degree to which the proposed activity can catalyse impact beyond a one-off project or programme investment” (Kasdan et al., 2021). This is achieved through either being multi-scale, i.e., having impact beyond the system boundaries, or through being scalable, i.e., expansion or replication elsewhere.

The ‘impact areas’ principle consists of two impact areas: governance on the one hand, beliefs and attitudes on the other hand. A change in governance or institutional arrangements may refer to a switch from top-down governance to bottom-up initiatives or co-production. This is the involvement of and interaction between different stakeholders in the planning of the project and the consideration of diverse views (Scolobig et al., 2023). The organisation of the adaptation solution should involve a variety of actors from (local) government employees through engineers or other experts to (private) stakeholders (Chu et al., 2019). Transformational adaptation typically requires an iterative decision-making process involving all these actors (Chhetri et al., 2019) to address the needs and challenges perceived by the community, as well as to enhance community resilience to change (Barnes et al., 2020). New forms of cooperation can arise between stakeholders and policymakers, for example, through knowledge networks (purpose-driven partnerships for cross-disciplinary dialogue, communication and cooperation across scientists and stakeholders) (Eikebrokk et al., 2021). In the city of Leuven in Belgium, for example, a membership organisation named “Leuven 2030” with over 400 members (citizens, civil society organisations, businesses, authorities) was founded with a focus to drive actions to accelerate the climate transition at local level. Also under governance, the adaptation solution may also affect policies or regulations. For example, the Delta Programme in the Netherlands, a large-scale adaptation programme, was introduced in 2010 to protect the country against the effects of sea-level rise. To ensure a long-term commitment to the programme, the Dutch government passed the Delta Act into law in 2012. With this Act, also a commissioner was assigned, responsible for the programme and the Delta Fund (Centre for Public Impact, 2019). Also, the Danish Ministry of Environment made an amendment to its Planning Act which required all municipalities to carry out climate risks assessments and integrate this into their local climate adaptation plans (Chu et al., 2019).

The second criterion in the impact areas principle relates to the public’s beliefs and attitudes. Transformational adaptation requires challenging existing norms and values (Deubelli & Mechler, 2021) and increasing willingness to take risks in the transition towards higher climate resilience (Watkiss & Cimato, 2020). Several cognitive biases exist which make people risk averse and unwilling to move away from the status quo in a disruptive—or transformational—way. Groupthink, for example, makes people reluctant to challenge previous decisions. Discipline-specific bias is a barrier to transformative solutions because individuals stick to their own discipline-specific knowledge (Kwan & Hung, 2025). For example, if decision making is in the hands of engineers, they will likely only come up with engineering-based solutions, not looking towards other disciplines. This criterion therefore assesses whether the adaptation

¹ Moore et al. (2015) make a distinction between scaling out (spreading and replicating transformation geographically), scaling up (uptake of transformational solutions in law, policy and institutions) and scaling deep (solutions that change beliefs and norms rooted in people, communities and cultures). Scalability in this case refers to the ‘scaling out’. As will be mentioned later, uptake into policy falls under the ‘governance’ criterion, while scaling deep is part of the ‘beliefs and attitudes’ criterion (both of these are part of the ‘Impact areas’ principle).

solution encourages out-of-the-box thinking. Encouraging the uptake of disruptive climate adaptation measures typically requires strong leadership (Chu et al., 2019).

The third principle 'depth' determines whether the system is truly changed by the adaptation solution (Fedele et al., 2019). The first criterion here is 'path-shifting', which means that the solution leads to a real break from the system's status quo. In other words, whether the system's current trajectory is altered towards a new direction. This may be an entirely new economic focus or a shift in location (Kates et al., 2012). For example, Métabief in France was previously a ski resort. Because of climate change, snowfall has decreased and artificial snow has become and will become even more so economically unviable. Because of this, the area is shifting its economic focus to other tourist activities such as mountain biking and hiking.

The second criterion 're-structuring' refers to the infrastructures, technologies or processes which are changed through the adaptation solution. The core focus of the system is not changed here, only the way things are done. An example of this is a shift from resource-intensive to regenerative agriculture. This changes agricultural practices and processes, but with the same goal of food production. A final criterion here is addressing root causes or drivers of climate or weather vulnerability rather than the symptoms or the proximate causes (Deubelli & Mechler, 2021; Scolobig et al., 2023). To achieve the aim of transformational adaptation, which is to increase resilience, addressing these root causes is crucial (Kasdan et al., 2021). When a municipality is vulnerable to floods, for example, a cause of this could be soil sealing due to increased urbanisation, meaning that the area is largely paved and there is insufficient water drainage. A solution which addresses the symptoms would be to install pipes which carry away the excess water, whereas a solution which addresses the root causes would be to make surfaces semipermeable, install green roofs and sustainable drainage systems throughout the municipality. The Room for the River programme in the Netherlands is a good example of how the root causes of flooding are targeted at the landscape scale. By relocating dikes (further away from the river), space is provided for flooding in natural floodplains instead of protecting cities with ever increasing dikes (Rijke et al., 2012). Bosomworth (2018) gives the example of treating bushfires as a hazard rather than addressing the underlying drivers of social and ecological vulnerabilities. Addressing the root causes also requires an a priori assessment of vulnerabilities and how they can be addressed holistically.

The principle 'temporality' relates the solution's time principle. The first criterion here is 'persistent' (Fedele et al., 2019), meaning that the adaptation solution is irreversible (without being rigid, as flexibility is needed). In other words, it leads to a long-term change and there is no intention to go back to the previous state. An investment criterion of the Green Climate Fund is financial viability in the long run or financial resources that provide for long-term sustainable continuation of the activities (Kasdan et al., 2021).

Secondly, the adaptation project should have a long-term vision, meaning that it foresees future climate risks rather than just past experienced risks. This requires an analysis of current and future climate risks during the project planning phase. The third criterion here is 'future benefits'. The adaptation solution should generate benefits over time. There is a clear difference with incremental adaptation in this regard, which focusses on solving current risks and needs (Chu et al., 2019). The benefits of an adaptation solution can also persist by sharing the lessons learnt from the project such that this learning can be incorporated into other projects (Kasdan et al., 2021). Because transformational adaptation involves fundamental changes in human and natural systems, the future impacts or benefits are likely difficult to foresee and uncertain (Kasdan et al., 2021; Walker et al., 2013). This brings us back to the risk-taking behaviour required for transformational adaptation. Acknowledging and quantifying uncertainty is thus a key aspect related to the study of transformational adaptation, so that we can identify robust transformations that show a satisfactory performance under most plausible futures (Adamson & Loch, 2021). The fourth criterion here is 'dynamic'. This means that the adaptation solution is able to be flexibly

adjusted as climatic conditions evolve (Termeer et al., 2017), not creating a lock-in (e.g. by building bikes that later on prove to be too low and get flooded). Note that within the temporality principle there is no reference to the speed of the change, a criterion used in the IPCC definition of transformational potential (O'Neill et al., 2022). Termeer et al. (2017) underline that long time frames are needed for true institutional changes. Also, over time, several incremental adaptation measures can cumulate and result in transformational change (Deubelli & Mechler, 2021; Kasdan et al., 2021). Yet, a bundling of adaptation solutions will result in transformative change if they part of a holistic programme, while avoiding maladaptation (e.g. through lock-in investments). Following this reasoning, transformational adaptation likely requires a portfolio of adaptation solutions (Kasdan et al., 2021).

Finally, there is the principle 'inclusivity'. This firstly means that the adaptation solution should be equitable. This means a fair distribution of benefits and losses across space, time and communities (Chu et al., 2019). The project should benefit vulnerable groups equally, if not disproportionately (Scolobig et al., 2023). For example, an urban greening project in a deprived neighbourhood is considered more equitable than one in a more affluent area, as it provides benefits such as improved health and social outcomes, and increased property values for disadvantaged communities. A transformational change may require the abandonment of old infrastructure and the construction of new more resilient infrastructure. There may, however, be people who rely on the old infrastructure and are therefore made more vulnerable with the change. This links into the concept of 'stranded assets', where assets or infrastructure becomes obsolete before its expected lifespan or before it has been repaid. Vulnerable groups should not only benefit from the intervention, they should also be prioritised in stakeholder engagement in the adaptation planning phase (Chu et al., 2019).

Moreover, an adaptation is considered 'synergetic' if it also contributes to climate change mitigation. This is the case when an adaptation solution reduces CO₂ emissions through, for example, carbon capture by trees or by using renewable energy for water treatment and distribution. Finally, if the project contributes to the achievement of additional Sustainable Development Goals—besides SDG13 'Climate action' and SDG 11 'Sustainable cities and communities', which are implicitly assumed to be addressed—it is considered 'SDG-aligned'. This means that an adaptation project might for example contribute to education (SDG4) by including an educative component (such as workshops or information boards), might support life below water (SDG 14) or life on land (SDG 15), might contribute to health (SDG3) by encouraging outdoor activity or to decent work and economic growth (SDG8) by providing sustainable employment opportunities. Kasdan et al. (2021) refer to these non-adaptation contributions as 'co-benefits'. Considering that the scorecard is a self-assessment tool, the user can self-decide to which extent criteria are fulfilled.

Figure 2: Illustration of the principles, criteria and indicators for transformational adaptation

Development of the TransformAr Scorecard based on indicators

The TransformAr Scorecard is an online self-assessment tool which consists of seven tabs: an introductory page with general information, a tab for each of the five principles and a final tab which presents a dashboard with results. The tool can be accessed via the TransformAr website². The original scorecard was developed based on the literature review from Section 2 and was then tested for five adaptation solutions to ensure that the indicators are feasible to answer (two of these case studies are included here, while another two are added in the appendix). This testing was done through interviews with project developers or civil servants involved in these solutions.

The first tab consists of three questions, regarding the nature of the adaptation solution, the scope and in which capacity the respondent is filling in the scorecard. Although these questions do not relate to the transformational adaptation principles and are not used for the calculation of the scores, they are important for the respondent to clearly define which actions the adaptation solution involves and what the boundaries of the solution are, in terms of geographic region and/or sector it is being applied to. For example, when the adaptation solution consists of an urban green space or park, is the geographic area defined as the entire municipality or only the neighbourhood in which it is implemented? This choice will influence the scores, as it is more challenging to influence an entire city than it is to influence a small neighbourhood. As will be mentioned in the Discussion, this subjectivity is a limitation of the scorecard. However, it is to the advantage of the respondent to answer the statements as truthfully as possible and with a critical mindset. Only in this way, the scorecard will reveal the adaptation solution's limitations from a transformational adaptation point of view and will offer opportunities to improve. The capacity in which the respondent is filling in the scorecard is important to frame their answers. For example, a project developer might be in possession of all of the information needed to complete the scorecard, but their answers may be less critical than those of an involved citizen.

² <https://scorecard.transformar.eu/>

In tabs two to six, the five transformational adaptation principles are covered (Tables 1-5). As mentioned in Section 2, each principle consists of several criteria. The scorecard provides a short description of the criterion along with an example of an adaptation project which is in line with this criterion. Each of the criteria is translated into at least one indicator (bullet points in the tables). Because the criteria are not quantifiable and there are no hard thresholds for deciding whether a criterion is met, these indicators are statements to be answered by the respondent with strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree or strongly agree. If the indicator is not at all applicable to the project, the respondent can answer 'not applicable' but respondents should attempt to answer all questions. The indicators thus lead to a value on a five-point scale.

Table 1: Criteria, examples and indicators for the principle 'Scope' (tab 2 in the questionnaire)

<p>Systemwide The adaptation project affects an entire region, sector or community, rather than a single component.</p> <p><i>Example: the city of Leuven (BE) has a climate strategy which affects the entire city and is not limited to a particular neighbourhood/street.</i></p> <p>Indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The adaptation solution affects a small part of the region/community/sector (identified in the introductory information), the majority remain unaffected • The change applies to the entire region/community/sector (identified in the introductory information) impacted by the project <p>Multi-scale The adaptation project has an impact across multiple scales, sectors, governmental levels.</p> <p><i>Example: Leuven's climate strategy impacts multiple sectors (tourism, mobility, green management, etc).</i></p> <p>Indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The adaptation project affects other regions/communities, besides the one which is directly impacted • The adaptation project involves multiple authorities (local, regional, national,...) • The adaptation project requires a pooling of financial resources (e.g., from different departments, combined public-private funding). In case of a publicly funded pilot project, it requires another funding source to go beyond the demo level • The adaptation project takes place on both public and private principle <p>Scalable The adaptation project can be spread and/or replicated geographically.</p> <p><i>Example: 'Tuinstraten' (Antwerp, BE) a project which started with the greening of a single street to improve water infiltration (flood protection), has the potential to be extended to entire neighbourhoods.</i></p> <p>Indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The adaptation project can easily be expanded to a larger area • The adaptation project has the potential to be replicated elsewhere • There is public outreach and/or interest for expanding the adaptation project beyond the current scope
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Table 2: Criteria, examples and indicators for the principle 'Impact areas' (tab 3 in the questionnaire)

<p>Beliefs and attitudes The adaptation project results in a change in beliefs among the public and policymakers towards risk tolerance, away from status quo bias and group thinking.</p> <p><i>Example: moving away from traditional grey infrastructure, such as the widening or replacement of sewer pipes for flood protection, towards less known nature-based solutions of which the long-term effects are perhaps less certain.</i></p> <p>Indicators:</p>

- The project raises awareness among the public on the challenges associated with climate change and the urgency to take action
- The adaptation project encourages project stakeholders to consider unknown approaches rather than sticking to traditional methods
- The actions taken by this adaptation project shift the mindset of policymakers and/or the public towards embracing risk in addressing climate challenges

Governance

The adaptation project involves adoption of alternative policy instruments or the involvement of and interaction between different stakeholders in the planning of the project and the consideration of diverse views.

Example: Eco-city Augustenborg (SE) was an urban regeneration project with extensive public consultation. Approximately 1 in 5 inhabitants was involved in the project planning phase.

Indicators:

- All decisions concerning the project planning are made by a small group of people
- The adaptation project leads to new forms of cooperation and coordination
- Citizens are involved in the planning of the adaptation project
- The adaptation project has led to new policies/regulations

Table 3: Criteria, examples and indicators for the principle 'Depth' (tab 4 in the questionnaire)

Path-shifting

Due to the adaptation project, the system's current trajectory is altered towards a new direction or economic orientation.

Example: the Ruhr area (DE) was previously focused on mining but is now the capital for design.

Indicators:

- The area has a different (economic) focus than prior to the adaptation project

Re-structuring

Reorganising existing structures, processes, or relationships to facilitate the change/improve climate resilience.

Example: rebuilding or redesigning critical infrastructure (e.g. energy grid) to withstand extreme weather, or a shift from resource-intensive to regenerative agriculture.

Indicators:

- The infrastructure/technologies/processes used are significantly affected by the adaptation project
- The adaptation project's approach has not previously been used in the area

Addressing root causes

The adaptation project addresses both the drivers of (climate) risk and vulnerabilities

Example: in Austria, flooding was a severe issue for households living along the Danube river, the root cause being that this area is not suitable for urbanisation. 500+ buildings have been relocated with the help of subsidies.

Indicators:

- It is clear which climate risk(s) is being addressed with the adaptation project
- It is known why the system was/is vulnerable to this climate risk
- The cause of this vulnerability is being addressed with the adaptation project

Table 4: Criteria, examples and indicators for the principle 'Temporality' (tab 5 in the questionnaire)

Persistent

The adaptation project leads to a long-term change, with no intention to go back to the previous state.

Example: permanent relocation of communities due to sea-level rise or severe flood risk.

Indicators:

- The changes initiated by the project will likely last
- There is no intention to reverse back to the state from before the change project

Long-term vision

The adaptation project considers future climate risks, not just past experienced risks.

Example: An urban greening project targeted at reducing the urban heat island effect also foresees nature-based solutions for future flood risk, which is at present not an issue in the area.

Indicators:

- Before the project planning/design, an analysis is done of the current and projected (climate) risks

Future benefits

The adaptation project generates benefits over time.

Example: the creation of buffer wetlands in the Ebro Delta (ES) created new habitats for birds and wildlife and has led to long-term climate resilience.

Indicators:

- The project provides benefits that will last over time, also after the project end date

Dynamic

The adaptation project allows for flexible adjustment to evolving (climatic) changes.

Example: transformation from traditional monoculture farming to an agroforestry system where tree species or crops can be rotated or introduced in response to changing climatic conditions.

Indicators:

- There is flexibility in the project to respond to new issues as they arise

Table 5: Criteria, examples and indicators for the principle 'Inclusivity' (tab 6 in the questionnaire)

Equitable

The adaptation project benefits vulnerable groups equally, if not disproportionately.

Example: an urban greening project near a social housing complex, benefitting the people living there.

Indicators:

- Vulnerable groups are considered during the design and implementation of the adaptation project
- Vulnerable groups are involved during the design and implementation of the adaptation project
- The adaptation project benefits vulnerable groups more than non-vulnerable groups (answer 'neutral' if the benefits are equal for both)
- The project will compensate losses for groups that are disadvantaged by the adaptation project

Synergetic

The adaptation project also contributes to climate change mitigation, besides adaptation, and has other environmental benefits.

Example: Local businesses in Bologna (IT) can offset their carbon footprint by paying for trees in the city, contributing to adaptation—the cooling effect of urban greening—and mitigation—CO2 capture by trees.

Indicators:

- Thanks to the adaptation project, CO2 emissions are reduced
- The adaptation project reduces pollution in the area
- The adaptation project contributes to the sustainable use of natural resources

SDG-aligned

The adaptation project addresses multiple of the Sustainable Development Goals, besides climate action.

Example: the creation of urban green spaces reduces urban heat island effects and improves air quality, benefitting people's wellbeing and physical and psychological health.

Indicators:

- The adaptation project contributes to poverty reduction (SDG1), offers employment opportunities (SDG8) and/or leads to economic growth (SDG8)
- The adaptation project contributes to biodiversity (life on land and/or under water) (SDG14, SDG15)
- The adaptation project does not discriminate between men and women (SDG5)
- There is an educational component linked to the adaptation project (e.g., workshops, courses) (SDG4)
- The adaptation project contributes to the health and wellbeing of its beneficiaries and nearby inhabitants (SDG3)

The final tab, the results dashboard, provides scores for each of the criteria individually. We refrain from providing an overall score for the transformational potential of an adaptation project because the scorecard is intended as a self-assessment tool to identify strengths and weaknesses. For example, an adaptation solution might not be of a large scope yet (neither systemwide nor multiscale) because it is in a demonstrator phase. It may still be considered transformational because there are clear plans for its upscaling (scalable). Taking a weighted average of the three scores might incorrectly lead to a low score for the principle scope. Hence, it is more valuable to provide the individual scores and guide the respondent in the interpretation of these scores. The respondents' answers from strongly disagree to strongly agree are recoded from zero to four. Negative indicators are coded the other way around, with strongly agree equal to zero³. Within each criterion, the scores for the indicators are averaged. An average score equal to or below one is considered insufficient, a score between one and three is neutral (there is room for improvement), while a score of three or above is considered good. There are some exceptions. For example, as a prerequisite for scoring highly on the principle 'SDG-aligned' an adaptation solution must score highly on the indicator about non-discrimination between men and women. The score for this criterion is then calculated as the mean score across the remaining four indicators. When a respondent answers 'not applicable' to an indicator, the average score is calculated using the remaining indicators for this criterion. If there is just one indicator, then no score can be generated for the criterion.

Case studies

To demonstrate the use of the scorecard and provide a clearer interpretation of the indicators, we here provide two examples. One of the cases is an example of an incremental adaptation solution; a combination of two digital tools which allows a Norwegian municipality to respond quicker and more appropriately to floods, without reducing exposure to increased stormwater. As mentioned by Park et al. (2012), adopting new technologies within an existing system is a typical example of incremental adaptation. The second case study can be considered a 'good example' as it scores well on all principles of transformational adaptation. It is a dune restoration programme along a part of the Catalan coast. Comparing the two allows us to draw lessons on how transformational adaptation can be and should be implemented in practice.

1.5 Case study 1: Stormwater management in Gjøvik, Norway

This first case study is an adaptation project implemented as part one of the demonstrators within the TransformAr project: stormwater management in the municipality of Gjøvik, Norway. This solution involves two initiatives: i) a citizen app in which citizens can report flooding events on their property or in their street to the municipality such that they alert the need for support from the municipality and ii) monitoring of water quantities and water quality in the stormwater pipes with sensors. Both solutions are considered together here and referred to as 'the adaptation project'. They contribute to an

³ An example of a negative statement is 'All decisions concerning the project planning are made by a small group of people', where strongly agree indicates a lack of stakeholder participation in the project planning phase.

integrative approach to fast detection of flooding events to enable prompt intervention and avoid damage as much as possible. As a result of climate change, extreme rainfall events have increased in frequency and floods have become an issue for the area. The solution is implemented by the municipality and is available to all its citizens. The 'system' is therefore geographically defined as the municipality of Gjøvik. The municipality serves as a replicator for solutions implemented in one of the other TransformAr demonstrators. The scorecard was filled in by one of the project developers responsible for the planning, design and implementation of the adaptation solution, but also part of the local government. In what follows, we will go over each of the transformational adaptation principles and provide justifications of the solution's scores on each of the criteria.

Firstly, the principle 'scope'. The Citizen App is useable by all citizens in the municipality, therefore influencing the entire system defined by the respondent, whereas the monitoring sensors are available in some parts of the municipality. The adaptation project is therefore considered systemwide. The project is very local, though, as it does not affect other areas beyond Gjøvik. During the project initiation phase, however, different levels of governance were involved in the identification of adaptation solutions (e.g., regional government, national meteorological agency). In this sense, the project can be considered multi-scale to some extent. The project is funded both with EU subsidies, through the TransformAr project, and with local funding. Other funding sources, such as private funds, are not used. After termination of TransformAr, the solutions will solely be funded by the municipality. Therefore, the adaptation project receives a 'neutral' score for the indicator on combined funding sources. Citizens can report flooding issues on their private property, yet, the project on its own does not affect their property physically. This distinction is therefore not applicable to the project. Gjøvik serves as a replicator in the TransformAr project. This means that it copies solutions from another demonstrator—the municipality of Lappeenranta in Finland has previously implemented these solutions—and analyses and communicates about this replicability. The solutions can therefore certainly be expanded to a larger area or replicated in other municipalities ('strongly agree' on both indicators). Information about the adaptation solution is communicated publicly to enable and encourage further expansion or replication of the solution. Despite this communication, there is no clear plan yet for expansion beyond the current demonstrators.

Secondly, the principle 'impact areas', referring to impacts on both the public's beliefs and attitudes and governance. Neither of the adaptation measures requires citizens to make investments, change their day-to-day lives or affect their private property. There is therefore no risk associated with the adaptation project for citizens and consequently no change in mindset regarding risk tolerance or embracing uncertain transformational approaches to climate adaptation. The Citizen App itself does raise awareness among its users on climate change by warning them about extreme rainfall events. Regarding a change in governance, the adaptation project scores relatively poorly. Most decisions regarding implementation of the solutions are made by a limited group of people from the municipality. However, an exploratory workshop with a wider group was done at the start of the project to identify potential adaptation solutions. This multi-stakeholder workshop involved individuals with different backgrounds and, as mentioned, from various levels of governance. The project has encouraged different departments within the municipality of Gjøvik to collaborate in a way which they previously did not and has led to new protocols and processes for managing flooding events. Nevertheless, there was very little citizen involvement throughout the design, planning and implementation phases of the adaptation solutions. The Citizen App was tested for usability with three to four citizens, but citizens were not asked about their needs and suggestions prior to the development of the app. Although crucial to transformational adaptation, co-creation and citizen involvement were both lacking for this project.

Thirdly, the principle 'depth'. The system, the municipality of Gjøvik, does not fundamentally change because of the adaptation project. The municipality does not have a different direction or economic focus after the adaptation solutions are implemented. The processes relating to stormwater management do change, however, affecting the municipality's daily operations. Through the app, citizens report flooding

issues which the municipality follows up on and responds to. Previously, in case of heavy rainfall, a civil servant would drive around the municipality, searching for places with flooding problems. Also, although not innovative from a global point of view, the citizen app and the monitoring sensors have not previously been used in the area.

At the start of the project, a climate risk analysis was done to assess the impacts of the current climate and future climate change on the municipality. The climate risk which is being addressed with the adaptation solution and which was identified during this risk analysis is increased heavy rainfall. Previously, rainfall was spread over longer periods, leaving time for the water to infiltrate. With the increasing frequency of extreme rainfall events, nature no longer has the capacity to cope with the excess water. The municipality is vulnerable to this risk because there is too much urbanisation (hard surfaces which do not allow for infiltration). Moreover, the stormwater pipes are insufficiently wide to carry away the water. The stormwater pipes, with a lifetime of about one hundred years, were designed for less extreme rainfall intensities (than currently observed). The two digital solutions provided by the project handle the consequences of heavy rainfall by rapidly responding to flood events, but they do not treat the root causes. Addressing landscape design (i.e., with flood retention measures), urbanisation and insufficiently wide stormwater pipes would require more comprehensive infrastructural changes, which are not foreseen within the project and would require significant amounts of funding.

Fourthly, the adaptation project scores highly on all criteria relating to the principle 'temporality'. Firstly, the solutions will remain in place also after termination of the TransformAr project. The municipality will carry the operating costs associated with this. This is partly made possible because additional features are included in the Citizen App (such as citizen complaints about littering) making it a useful tool for the municipality, beyond flood management. An analysis of future climate risks, both at the local and the regional level, was done prior to the project to ensure that the solutions provides sufficient benefits also in the future. Moreover, the two solutions can be flexibly adapted to the evolving climate. For example, the sensors can be relocated and other weather events can be integrated into the Citizen app (e.g., communication to citizens about drought events or the reporting of issues caused by snowfall).

Finally, the principle 'inclusivity'. All of Gjøvik's citizens were considered during the implementation phase of the solutions. For example, the user interface of the Citizen App was tested, keeping in mind the needs of more digitally illiterate people. However, no special attention was given to more vulnerable groups and the project does not benefit vulnerable people more than non-vulnerable people. It is assumed, for example, that everyone is in the possession of a smartphone and has access to internet. Also, in the responding to reported issues by citizens no priority is given to vulnerable people (e.g., elderly or economically disadvantaged people). The adaptation solution does not directly contribute to climate mitigation. It indirectly contributes to reduced emissions and pollution by reducing the need for transport for surveillance in the case of floods, but the impact of this on the municipality's carbon footprint is minimal. Neither do the adaptation solutions contribute to any of the other sustainable development goals mentioned in the scorecard. The monitoring sensors do not only measure water quantities but also water quality. In this way, the municipality can monitor the water which is being released into the lake. However, there is no link with the water treatment facility so there is no real impact on the lake's biodiversity, for example.

Figure 3: TransformAR Scorecard results dashboard for the Gjøvik case study

The figure above shows the dashboard generated by the tool. For each criterion, a colour code is shown which offers an indication of how well the project scores. Based on this dashboard, a few suggestions for improvement can be identified. Firstly, the adaptation project’s scope could be increased by collaborating with the regional authorities (e.g., proposing the solutions to be implemented outside of Gjøvik) or by expanding the solutions through different funding sources. Secondly, although both solutions contribute to responding more rapidly to heavy rainfall events, the adaptation project does not fundamentally change the system. Some processes within the local government are altered, but the adaptation project does not affect the municipality’s general focus or the day-to-day lives of its citizens. Thirdly, as co-production is a crucial part of transformational adaptation, future changes to either of the solutions should ideally be consulted with citizens. What are the needs of citizens with regards to the Citizen App, for example? Is the process of reporting flooding events sufficiently user-friendly? Are there additional features which they need? How can the municipality, according to them, best respond to floods and avoid damage? Fourth, special consideration of vulnerable citizens is advised. Even to date, after implementing both solutions, vulnerable citizens, such as elderly people, can still be considered by questioning them about their satisfaction with the Citizen App. What could be improved or which alternatives could be provided to ensure that they benefit from the solutions at least as much as non-vulnerable citizens? And finally, there is potential for the project to generate co-benefits, besides stormwater management. The project could help mitigate climate change, for example, by integrating energy-saving advice for citizens in the Citizen App, raising awareness about energy consumption and carbon-based transport. Also, by integrating the water quality monitoring with a water treatment facility, the project could significantly contribute to ‘clean water’ (SDG6), for example.

1.6 Case study 2: Dune restoration along the Catalan Coast, Spain

The second case study is an adaptation project implemented as part one of the demonstrators within the IMPETUS project: sand dune restoration along the Catalan Coast, Spain. Within the IMPETUS project, the University of Girona is carrying out an assessment of the effectiveness of nature-based solutions to preserve sand dunes. The measures are implemented on three different types of beaches: urban, semi-urban and semi-natural beaches across two different areas along the Catalan Coast: in the North, Costa Brava (natural and semi-urban), and in the South, Costa Daurada (urban). The actions which are being implemented consist of sand fences, rope fences and ceasing to use machines to clean the beaches. These

measures are taken by the local authorities themselves. Before and after the actions, drone monitoring (with lidar, RGB and multispectral sensors) is done to create digital elevation models and surface models. These models give insights into the morphometric characteristics of the beaches (e.g., beach profile, volumetry) and allow the researchers to assess the efficiency of the measures. The 'system' is geographically defined as the Catalan Coast. The scorecard was filled in by one of the project developers responsible for the assessment of the measures, a geographer. In collaboration with other universities, the University of Girona is developing a multi-disciplinary criterion for dune restoration potential (based on a set of variables derived from geography, biology, etc). In what follows, we will go over each of the transformational adaptation principles and provide justifications of the solution's scores on each of the criteria.

Regarding the principle 'scope', firstly, the two municipalities where the measures are being taken and the monitoring is done are just a small part of the Catalan Coast. In that sense, the project cannot be considered 'systemwide'. However, the recommendations for dune restoration which will result from the project are applicable to the entire coastline. Due to the currents, going from North to South, the measures being taken also benefit the beaches more southwards due to increased sediment. However, these benefits are not measured within the project. The project is highly multi-scale. Firstly, because it requires involvement of authorities at multiple levels. The measures are taken at the local level; municipalities manage the use of their own beaches. Beach regeneration decisions are taken both at the local and regional level, while the financing is provided at the national level through the General Directorate of Coasts and Marine Environment of the Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge, who is responsible for the protection and regulation of coastal areas. The project is financed through a range of different channels. The assessment part of the project is funded through the EU-subsidised IMPETUS project, while the measures in Costa Brava are paid by the National Park (which receives funding from the regional government) as the beach is part of this protected area, and the measures in the Costa Daurada are paid by the municipality itself (which receives funding from the state). Although the coastline is public principle, there are some privatised areas, such as campsites. These private stakeholders are asked to help restoring the beaches. Although the measures are currently implemented in only two municipalities, project is highly scalable. The measures are cheap to implement, while it is much more costly to recover from damage after coastal erosion has taken place. Therefore, there is clear potential for the project to be expanded along the entire Catalan Coast or replicated elsewhere. The recommendations with regard to which measures to implement can be transferred to other coastal regions. There is already a follow-up project⁴ where the assessments will be repeated in Calafell as a continuation of the IMPETUS project. It will also extend to other parts of Catalonia and the south of France.

Secondly, the principle 'impact areas'. Within the adaptation project, a lot of effort is put into dissemination of the results to the public—through talks at city halls and universities, for example—to create awareness on the impacts of coastal erosion and the actions which are needed. There is also a change in willingness to actively take part in coastal restoration. For example, two campsites were asked to implement natural measures on their beaches. One of the two agreed and the results showed significantly larger sediment volumes on that part of the beach. This has encouraged the other campsite to acknowledge the benefit of these measures and increased their willingness to adapt. The adaptation solutions are also in line with the national government's aim to stop artificial nourishment of beaches. The results of this project contribute to this shift in mindset. This principle also relates to impacts on governance. The natural measures which were implemented were chosen by a small group of people. Both Calafell municipality, located in the Costa Daurada, and the National Park of Aiguamolls de l'Empordà managers, in the Costa Brava, hired technicians to advise them on which measures to

⁴ The project is part of the INTERREG - POCTEFA framework.

implement and how, but the decisions themselves were taken by a limited group of people within each of these organisations. Although there was thus no ‘co-creation’ with citizens within the project, the perceived acceptance of stakeholders was taken into account. If a measure was believed not to be accepted by the public, it was not chosen. Also, if the campsites did not want to take a certain measure, they were free not to do it. Although there is no direct impact of the adaptation project on policies and regulations, the current policies are in favour of nature-based solutions and the findings of this project support this. There is thus, an indirect contribution.

Thirdly, the principle ‘depth’. The project does not change the (economic) focus of the system and is therefore not considered ‘path-shifting’. The area mostly has a touristic orientation and the natural preservation of dunes allows this economy to persist. Without the measures, the beaches would degrade and tourism would be jeopardised. Naturally preserved beaches and dunes attract a different type of tourist than previously, though, those that attach more value to nature. The adaptation programme is highly ‘re-structuring’ because it introduces an entirely different approach to restoring beaches than before, when beaches were nourished artificially. Although these natural measures were used decades ago, artificial replenishment took over to satisfy the beach styles demanded by tourists. The measures have been reintroduced and are perceived as new by the area’s users. The risk which is addressed with this adaptation programme is storm erosion/coastal erosion and flooding, caused by a lack of sediment. This is not a result of climate change, but is the result of a change in activities and land use changes. This change in activities is referred to as littoralization, or economic overdevelopment or urbanisation concentrated along coastlines. This littoralization leads to ‘coastal squeeze’, where human-made structures cover the natural spaces such as dunes needed to prevent this erosion. Furthermore, due to artificialisation inland, sediment is no longer flowing to rivers and from rivers to the coast. Climate change is increasing this risk, but the root vulnerability is not due to climate change. This adaptation programme does not address this root cause. Rather, it addresses the symptoms by retaining sediment through natural measures.

Fourthly, the principle ‘temporality’. For the changes initiated by the adaptation programme to last, maintenance is needed. It is not sufficient to install rope fences, for example, and then leave them unattended. Although there is no intention to reverse back to the state from before the adaptation programme, the measures’ persistence will depend on whether funding is available for maintenance. This funding comes from national annual budgets and therefore relies on whether there is sufficient interest and awareness among politicians to put erosion on the agenda. The future of this adaptation programme is thus uncertain, leading to a ‘neutral’ score on persistence. The natural restoration measures can be flexibly adjusted to newly arising conditions on a yearly basis, for example, a change in wind direction. The assessments done by the University of Girona will lead to recommendations regarding which measures are most effective in preserving beaches. By disseminating these results, the project will likely generate benefits beyond the end date of the IMPETUS project and beyond the current programme scope.

Lastly, the principle ‘inclusivity’. Although the decisions relating to which measures to implement were taken by a small group of local decisionmakers, the needs of vulnerable people were considered. For example, footpaths were created which allow the beaches to be accessible to people with limited mobility. In the short run, restaurant holders will be disadvantaged by the adaptation programme because their terraces are not compatible with the natural measures. However, in the long run, the natural measures prevent the beaches from degrading which allows restaurant holders to stay in business. Therefore, although the restaurant holders consider themselves among the vulnerable group, they are not considered nor compensated within the adaptation programme. The project also has several co-benefits, although these are not explicit goals of the project. Through the adaptation programme, additional vegetation is created on beaches which in turn reduces carbon dioxide concentrations, recreates dune habitats and increases biodiversity. Previously contaminated areas are turned into natural

spaces, reducing pollution. The project contributes to a socially, economically and environmentally sustainable use of the beach-dune system. This system was previously destroyed, leaving only the beach part of this system. Economically sustainable here refers to the avoided cost of artificially restoring and nourishing beaches and ensuring the livelihoods of people who depend on these beaches. Although the adaptation programme does not create any employment opportunities or economic growth, it ensures that the current economy can continue to exist. Without natural dune restoration, the coast will degrade and many economic activities will be lost. The adaptation programme contributes to biodiversity on land (through increased vegetation) and under water. The educational component of the adaptation project is realised through thorough public outreach (television, media, universities, conferences for citizens, etc). Finally, the programme contributes to the health and wellbeing of nearby inhabitants through improved air quality and creating nature-rich spaces for outdoor recreation.

Figure 4: TransformAR Scorecard results dashboard for the Catalonia case study

All these findings lead to the above results dashboard. The general assessment of this case study is positive. Although the measures themselves are being implemented in a small area, these measures are part of a wider programme which will likely affect other regions and there are clear plans for extending the project beyond the current scope. Looking at the results dashboard, three improvements can be suggested from a transformational adaptation point of view. Firstly, the adaptation programme does not shift the economic focus of the area, which is tourism. Tourism or increased urbanisation contributes to the rapid degradation of beaches. To address this root cause, the programme could be more 'path-shifting', i.e., contribute to the rise of alternative economic activities (e.g., ecotourism). Secondly, the programme does not involve a wide range or large group of stakeholders in the planning and implementation process. To increase acceptance for certain measures—from restaurant holders, for example—a more bottom-up decision-making process may have been advisable. Transformational adaptation typically requires new forms of collaboration. Lastly, and relating to the previous point, the adaptation programme prioritises environmental goals and does not involve or compensate those groups which might be disadvantaged by the project. In order for a transformational adaptation programme to be sustainable in the long term, there should be wide societal acceptance.

1.7 Comparison of case studies

The two case studies covered here represent a more incremental and a more transformational example of adaptation, respectively. Although it is clear from these case studies that this distinction is not black and white. Both case studies have positive and negative aspects to them, from a transformational adaptation point of view. In terms of geographic scale, both case studies take place at the municipality level and potentially apply to all citizens living in these municipalities. However, overall, we can conclude that the digital solutions introduced in the Gjøvik case study have little influence on the day-to-day lives of inhabitants and do not contribute to preventing damage from flood events. Rather, the solutions help reducing damage after the event has occurred. The dune restoration programme in Catalonia, although not targeting the root causes of littoralization (cf. economic overdevelopment of coasts), focuses much more on preventing damage. Through nature-based solutions, sediment is increased and coastal erosion is reduced. This ensures that the current economy, focused on tourism, can persist. Through nature-based solutions the Catalan case study has several co-benefits such as contributing to biodiversity and reducing greenhouse gas emissions. These types of co-benefits are much harder to achieve with technological advancements or digital tools. So, in line with Park et al. (2012), these case studies confirm that adopting new technologies within an existing system cannot be considered transformational.

Both case studies lack stakeholder engagement or interdisciplinary decision making. In both case studies, all decisions are made by a small group of people from the respective municipalities. Transformational adaptation requires new forms of governance, including bottom-up decision making and co-creation. This leads to broader acceptance of the measures, on the one hand, and ensures that everyone's needs are met—especially those of vulnerable citizens, on the other hand. Moreover, having citizens invest in an adaptation project, for example by actively taking part in the planning or by implementing measures on their private principle, is likely more effective in raising awareness on climate change and urgency to act than solely communicating about adaptation. The importance of co-production and stakeholder engagement is further demonstrated by two Horizon Europe projects, CLIMAS and Adaptation AGORA, which both focus on developing methods for generating greater interest, engagement and co-creation and implementation of climate adaptation plans.

Complementarity between the TransformAr Scorecard and other assessment tools

In the field of climate adaptation, users may benefit from the TransformAr Scorecard because of its potential to identify how an adaptation solution can be modified in order to lead to long-term, systemic, transformational changes. This aspiration ties in with the development and potential of other tools for adaptation, in a complementary manner. The tools listed below, similarly to the scorecard, are also self-assessment tools related to adaptation and can be filled out before, during or after an adaptation solution or project is implemented. They vary in their usage, inputs and outputs. A tabular comparison of the tools, while also giving references on where to find them is provided in the Appendix.

- Adaptation Policy Credibility tool (APC) assesses the level of progress of climate change adaptation policies
- REGILIENCE Self-Assessment Tool on Maladaptation focuses on spotting potential risk factors for maladaptation
- Pathways2Resilience (P2R) Self-assessment evaluates the capacity for climate resilience of local authorities and is used for assessing funding eligibility
- Resilience Maturity Model supports cities in identifying their resilience stage and then helps to identify the correct policies to implement in order to evolve and increase their maturity

- UNDRR Make Cities Resilient by 2030 (MCR2030) Resilience roadmap is a 3-stage roadmap to urban resilience for cities, linked to an initiative which increases cities’ resilience through a knowledge-sharing network MCR2030
- Climate Change Adaptation Scoring Tool (Euro LCP Initiative) is an online tool to score adaptation plans along five dimensions
- Adaptation Good Practice Checklist Toolkit is a tool which aids the development of good adaptation proposals for funding from the Green Climate Fund, Adaptation Fund, etc.
- Adaptation preparedness scorecards for the TransformAr demonstrators (D3.1), based on the European Commission’s scorecards used by EU member states in the context of the EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change.

Figure 5: (a) REGILIENCE Maladaptation checklist, (b) Adaptation preparedness scorecard

There are various similarities and differences between these tools and the scorecard. The P2R tool, the resilience maturity model and the Make Cities Resilient tool assess the organisational/institutional maturity to proceed towards transformational adaptation, whereas the Adaptation Policy Credibility (APC) tool and Euro LCP initiative assess existing adaptation plans and policies. The TransformAr scorecard screens the transformational potential of adaptation solutions or programmes (while not considering the resilience maturity of the system). The REGILIENCE maladaptation tool assesses whether a solution will lead, or has resulted, in maladaptation. An analysis of the low scores (e.g., low score on inclusivity) shows insights in potential avenues of improvement. An overall trend in these tools is that they provide information on the degree to which certain aspects are addressed by adaptation projects, based on the project-specific variables or processes given as input by the users. Overall, these tools aim to bring the attention of users to aspects which they may not have considered beforehand. We presume that exchange amongst colleagues about the output of each tool and across the different tools will enhance their complementarity and strengthen the associated adaptation solutions.

The scorecard is considered a valuable addition to these previously published assessment tools. The scorecard specifically focuses on the transformational component of adaptation, which is rather weak, undefined or absent in the other tools. The P2R tool does also have an explicit component on transformational adaptation, in addition to other aspects of adaptation maturity at organisational level. The scorecard is also solution oriented as it screens adaptation solutions for its transformative potential, and hence providing opportunities for improvement. The scorecard is finally user-friendly and provides first insights to users in less than 1 hour (which could be an incentive for the actual use).

The scorecard also comes with some drawbacks. The TransformAr Scorecard is more useful when used as a tool to assess the transformational potential of an adaptation solution ex ante, as this still allows for adjustments to the design and implementation of the solution (i.e., if citizens were originally not involved in co-production it may not be too late to still do so). However, before implementing the project, the respondent may not have all the information required to fill in the questionnaire. Ex post, all the

information is available but it may be too late to intervene. For example, if an urban greening project is placed in a high-income residential area with little benefit to vulnerable citizens the project scores lowly on 'equitable', but there may be no opportunity to solve this anymore.

A second limitation of the TransformAr Scorecard is reliability. In other words, if the scorecard were to be filled in by another respondent, in the same or another capacity, the obtained scores would likely differ. This is due to both subjectivity and differences in interpretation. To illustrate the former: a project developer who was involved in every stage of the adaptation solution, from design to implementation to upscaling, will likely be less critical of the solution than a local inhabitant who feels that they do not sufficiently benefit from the solution. This clearly demonstrates the subjectivity of the scorecard. The latter refers to a different understanding of the indicators. The indicators were developed in such a way that they can be answered for very different types of adaptation solutions (e.g., digital solutions versus infrastructural projects), leading them to be very general and broad. This implies that they can be interpreted in different ways, potentially resulting in different scores. A solution to both sources of unreliability could be to have the scorecard filled in by different types of respondents (project developers, local authorities, beneficiaries, etc.) and to average their scores, where the first respondent also provides justification for their answers such that the interpretation of the subsequent respondents aligns.

A third limitation, closely related to the previous one, is validity. It is not possible to question respondents directly about the criteria (e.g., asking a project developer whether they consider their project 'systemwide' or 'multiscale' would lead to discussion on terminology and concepts, rather than a pragmatic assessment). The criteria therefore had to be translated to concrete indicators, which have a clearer interpretation and are easy to answer for anyone who is in possession of the adaptation project's information. We cannot be certain, however, that with these indicators we are actually measuring the underlying criteria, or 'latent' variables. Also, the scorecard may not cover all aspects related to transformational adaptation. Some authors state that an adaptation solution should be innovative for it to be considered transformational, while others claim that the interventions should be novel for the area but not innovative in absolute terms. Related to this, it is important to stress location or context dependency. What is transformational in one place is not necessarily transformational in another place, where the same adaptation strategy might already be well established. A condition important for transformational change is thus 'the level of departure versus the outcome level of change' (e.g., to what extent has governance changed, have the mindsets of people changed, have functions changed as opposed to before the intervention) (Watkiss & Cimato, 2020). Transformational adaptation is therefore a relative concept. Each of the criteria mentioned above should therefore be assessed in the context of the local adaptation solution (Kasdan et al., 2021).

It is furthermore to be noted that the scorecard does not provide quantitative insights on how effective a solution is in terms of increasing climate resilience or reducing the risks associated with extreme weather events. The scorecard is intended to assess the holistic aspects of a transformation. Since also the other listed tools target the policy/organisational component of climate adaptation, also the other tools do not have this component of quantitative adaptation effectiveness. Only Resilience Maturity Model provides a list of more objectively assessable indicators, such as the number of trained volunteers or the number of weakness assessments. The quantitative scoring of adaptation effectiveness is outside of the scope of this paper, and also at the international level still subject of debate. In the EU, and also at the UN, an agreed list of indicators (and associated methods) to measure the impact of adaptation solutions is still pending.

The drawbacks of reliability and validity however can be seen as relative drawbacks. The majority of tools are self-assessment tools and are intended at providing non-binding insights to the users. The interpretation of the results depends largely on the intention of the user. If the tool is used to demonstrate how well a particular solution has worked, the user will likely score higher compared to a

user that aims to criticise the project. Additionally, if the tools were to be used for official reporting of how a region or city progresses on transformational adaptation or connected to the monitoring and evaluation of project funding, the reliability and validity becomes essential, as it intends to document that the project's money is well spent and led to actual societal impacts.

Conclusion

In this guidance document, we build further on the policy brief 'Understanding Transformational Adaptation' written under the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change's Implementation Platform by developing a scorecard to assess the transformational character of a climate adaptation project. With this, we aim to bridge the gap between the academically defined term 'transformational adaptation' and its implementation in practice. Based on literature, we identify five principles of transformational adaptation—scope, depth, impact areas, temporality and inclusivity—each consisting of several criteria. These criteria are translated into indicators, easily graspable and answerable for the non-academic audience. Using this scorecard, local authorities or other contributors to an adaptation programme or project can identify the strengths and weaknesses of their project from a transformational adaptation point of view.

To illustrate the use of the tool, we describe two case studies from EU projects. The results show that an adaptation project is not either incremental or transformational, but it can have aspects from both. Note that the scorecard does not assess the effectiveness of an adaptation solution in terms of increasing climate resilience or reducing the risks associated with extreme weather events. For this we refer to some of the other tools discussed Section 0. It purely assesses whether the project adheres to the principles of transformational adaptation, on the premises that transformational adaptation is needed to enhance systems' resilience under the rapidly changing climate.

The scorecard will help decisionmakers consider all aspects of transformational adaptation. Highlighting where the weaknesses lie, this tool can help decisionmakers in making their adaptation programmes more transformational and thus more impactful and durable. In this way, the tool contributes to greater climate resilience through more effective, large-scale and widely accepted adaptation solutions and programmes.

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Appendix

A. Other tools for assessing adaptation and/resilience

Tool	Format	Target audience	Output	Comparison with TransformAr Scorecard	
				Similarities	Differences
Adaptation Policy Credibility tool⁵ (APC) assesses the level of progress of climate change adaptation policies	Excel checklist which covers policy, economic, scientific and technical credibility and legitimacy related to adaptation planning	Anyone involved in local climate adaptation plans (municipality level)	Composite credibility index and sub-indices per category	Identifying areas for potential improvement Learning and sharing lessons learnt	Tracking adaptation policy processes Generates a composite credibility index (the TransformAr Scorecard does not lead to an overall score)
REGIANCE Self-assessment tool on maladaptation⁶ focuses on spotting potential risk factors for maladaptation	PDF 4-page checklist covering questions on the topics: risks and vulnerabilities, developing the adaptation strategy, expected impacts, monitoring and evaluating	Anyone in charge of planning and implementing regional adaptation actions. It can be used on a local, individual or national (by both public and private organisations) level	Overview of answers to all questions (yes, no, partially) and room for justification of choices	Self-assessment considering aspects separately rather than presenting a composite score One question on the consideration of transformational change options	Specific focus lies on risks of maladaptation: avoid that adaptation actions cause increased vulnerability or harm to livelihoods, ecosystems, and the economy
Pathways2Resilience Self-assessment⁷ evaluates the	Excel with a total of 178 questions covering	Public authorities	Excel generates an overview of scores for	An overview of scores for the different categories	The results of the assessment are used to

⁵ https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/mission/external-content/pdfs/008-assesstemplate_apctool-ed2.xlsx/@@download/file

⁶ <https://regiance.eu/self-assessment-tool-for-maladaptation/>

⁷ <https://www.pathways2resilience.eu/The-P2RSelf-Assessment-Questionnaire>

Tool	Format	Target audience	Output	Comparison with TransformAr Scorecard	
				Similarities	Differences
capacity for climate resilience of local authorities and is used for assessing funding eligibility	different phases of adaptation strategy development, the investment plan and key enabling conditions for climate resilience		different elements and a composite score, these are displayed on spider diagrams	Includes a score on transformative capacity	<p>determine whether the municipality is eligible for funding from P2R</p> <p>The goal is to repeat the assessment after an adaptation project has taken place to monitor progress</p> <p>Very extensive and time-consuming questionnaire</p>
Resilience Maturity Model ⁸ supports cities in identifying their resilience stage and then helps to identify the correct policies to implement in order to evolve and increase their maturity	PDF or Excel table for exploring policy options in the categories: leadership & governance, preparedness, infrastructure & resources and cooperation.	Public authorities	The model does not generate any output based on respondent input. It is a matrix of policy options on which cities can position themselves in terms of resilience maturity and get inspiration for policy actions	Addresses similar topics as the TransformAr Scorecard: flexibility, awareness raising, co-production	<p>Focuses on cities</p> <p>Does not require respondent input</p> <p>Includes a list of objective indicators (e.g., number of trained volunteers or number of assessments of weaknesses) rather than respondent-based statements</p>

⁸ <https://smr-project.eu/tools/maturity-model-guide/>

Tool	Format	Target audience	Output	Comparison with TransformAr Scorecard	
				Similarities	Differences
UNDRR MCR2030 Resilience roadmap ⁹ is a 3-stage roadmap to urban resilience for cities, linked to an initiative which increases cities' resilience through a knowledge-sharing network MCR2030	A Google form where respondents are asked about 1) their disaster risk reduction/resilience strategy and 2) awareness raising activities	Local governments that want to take part in the 'Making cities resilient' (MCR2030) initiative, a knowledge and resource-sharing initiative for cities to become more resilience to disaster	The form results in which stage on the resilience roadmap the city is: A, B or C. The website then provides guidance on moving to the next stage and allows cities to join the initiative.	The form asks about disaster risk/resilience awareness raising among the public and government officials	The tool is a requirement for joining the MCR2030 initiative Assessment is based on only very few questions
Climate Change Adaptation Scoring Tool ¹⁰ (Euro LCP Initiative) is an online tool to score adaptation plans along five dimensions	An online tool to score adaptation plans in terms of prior research, adaptation goals, measures, implementation, monitoring and evaluation and participation	Anyone involved in local climate adaptation plans	Bar charts with a composite score for the adaptation plan, with a subdivision of scores per category (3 bar charts, for 3 different weighting options)	Addresses similar topics as the TransformAr Scorecard: climate-vulnerable groups, identification of specific climate risks, about other sustainability-related benefits, financial resources	Elaborate tool, which requires a lot of information about the respondent (log in) and the project Responses are stored and can be adjusted later
Adaptation Good Practice Checklist Toolkit ¹¹ is a tool which aids the development of good adaptation proposals for funding from the Green Climate Fund, Adaptation Fund, etc.	A PDF to score adaptation plans along 9 'adaptation good practices' with several criteria per good practice	Local and national authorities responsible for the roll out of adaptation plans	A score (red/amber/green) for each good practice, equal to the lowest score for any of the criteria for that practice	Addresses similar topics as the TransformAr Scorecard: stakeholder engagement, gender equality, identifying climate risks	Focus on Africa

⁹ <https://mcr2030.undrr.org/resilience-roadmap/stage-assessment>

¹⁰ <https://www.lcp-initiative.eu/climate-change-scoring-tool/>

¹¹ <https://www.icvanetwork.org/resource/adaptation-good-practice-checklist-toolkit-checklist/>

B. Case studies

Case study: Urban regeneration in Bilbao, Spain

To demonstrate the use of the Scorecard and provide a clearer interpretation of the statements, we here provide an example. The covered case study is an urban regeneration programme, which consists of separate projects in various neighbourhoods in the city of Bilbao. An example of these projects, which is currently ongoing, is the transformation of the Zorrotzaurre peninsula into a residential and flood-proof island. Although the transformation of the city was originally initiated because of a devastating flood event in 1983, the main purpose of the change programme is not to make the city more climate resilient. It is therefore not considered a climate adaptation programme. The ‘system’ is geographically defined as the metropolitan area of Bilbao, where the neighbourhoods are tackled one after the other. The Scorecard was filled in by an advisor from the climate adaptation department at Technalia, a Spanish research organisation which works together with regions and cities. Technalia has been advising the municipality since the beginning of its transformation in the 1990s. In what follows, we will go over each of the transformational adaptation domains and provide justifications of the solution’s scores on each of the characteristics.

Figure B - 1: Render of the Zorrotzaurre island/peninsula after the regeneration (source: zorrotzaurre.com)

Scope

The adaptation programme affects the entire city. It is organised as a programme of different regeneration projects in different neighbourhoods, little by little covering the entire metropolitan area. Most measures are not driven by climate change, although converting the peninsula to an island, for example, was necessary to improve the flood performance of the entire city. The programme also generates benefits beyond the city borders, by attracting tourism to the region.

At the time of the flooding event in 1983, it was agreed among regional, provincial and local governments to take action, while bringing on board also national administrations (such as the national railways). Also the financing of Bilbao’s transformation has come from these various levels of administration. Part of the success of the programme comes from innovative financial mechanisms and a combination of instruments (e.g., a public society for land management with a common pot of public land). There are also mechanisms in place to reinvest the new developments’ returns into new infrastructure. The urban regeneration measures require agreements between public decisionmakers and private developers, so there is strong involvement from private stakeholders although the financial resources coming from private players is limited. Most large infrastructure investments come

from taxation if private developers. The interventions take place mostly on the public domain, although expropriation of households was necessary for some projects.

The programme has been expanding over the years. The initial regeneration projects took place in the city centre, while more recent projects are covering other parts of Bilbao. There is great potential to adopt similar approaches and to replicate this programmes in other cities in Spain and beyond. Bilbao has been receiving international delegations with interest in replicating the transformation programme in their cities. It is perceived as an excellent example of transformational change.

Impacts

Because the focus of the change programme is not climate adaptation, there is little awareness raising on climate change challenges. Neither is there an increased willingness to take risk with regards to addressing climate challenges. The change programme is considered more of a modernisation process.

Although the programme involves many different administrative levels, the majority of the decisions are taken by a small group of people at the municipality. The municipality has most control over the changes. Governance among all the different level is a very new way of cooperating, though. Citizens are not involved in the individual regeneration projects, there is no bottom-up coordination. There was some participation by citizens in the development of the urban master plan, consulting with citizens what the city should look like in the future. The programme has had an influence on policies regulations. For example, it has affected building regulations through the modification of ordinances.

Depth

Thanks to the adaptation programme, there has been a drastic growth in tourism which has lead to a shift in the economic focus of the metropolitan area. There is also a significant change in the city's infrastructure, through the various regeneration projects. Although the city was originally inspired by other projects internationally, Bilbao is now a reference for regeneration projects worldwide.

The metropolitan area of Bilbao is vulnerable to flooding due to its high exposure. To some extent, the city is made more climate resilient by taking certain exposure-reducing measures but, as mentioned, addressing this risk is not the core aim of the change programme.

Temporality

Both the physical (infrastructural) and the governance changes which have resulted from the adaptation programme will last in the future. There is no intention to reverse back to the previous state. Because this programme is part of a regeneration strategy for the city, there is a long time horizon foreseen for this programme. The programme has been ongoing for more than thirty years, and some transformations are still pending.

No analysis was done of current an projected climate risks, so these risks were not purposely taken into account in the planning or design of the adaptation programme. Although infrastructural works are mostly irreversible, there is some room for flexibility in the decision making for urban development. For example, new plans can be adjusted to investors' demands or the speed of urban development can be adjusted. Flexibility is needed to ensure the success of the overall process.

Inclusivity

An integral part of urban regeneration is trying to overcome social exclusion. For this reason, economically vulnerable groups were considered, for example, through the development of social housing. Also high-income groups benefit from the regeneration programme, so there is no disproportionate advantage for vulnerable groups. Anyone who is drastically affected by the regeneration programme (e.g., relocation) is appropriately compensated.

Due to the programme, there is increased public transport and reduced traffic which leads to a decrease in pollution and CO2 emissions. The adaptation programme therefore contributes to climate mitigation. Also a reduction in water pollution, soil decontamination/reclamation and environmental restoration were among the main goals of the transformation.

Because of the growth of the tourism sector, the city has benefitted from significant economic growth and an increase in employment opportunities. There has been a lot of public outreach about the project meaning that there is also a limited educational component. Lastly, through the regeneration programme the health and wellbeing of Bilbao’s citizens is increased. For example, by increasing access to recreational areas.

Results

Figure B-2: TransformAR Scorecard results dashboard for the Bilbao case study

The transformational character of the programme is generally assessed positively. The programme covers an (increasingly) large area, many levels of governance are involved and there is significant potential for replication. The city is drastically changed, both its infrastructure as well as its economic focus. Because the programme is not intended at climate change adaptation, it does not score well on assessing and addressing the root causes of current and future climate change. It also does not lead to a significant change in the mindsets of policy makers and the public towards urgency to take climate action.

Case study: Room for the River programme in the Netherlands

To demonstrate the use of the Scorecard and provide a clearer interpretation of the statements, we here provide an example. The case study covered is one of the programmes most often cited in the transformational adaptation literature: the Room for the River programme (2006-2019) in the Netherlands. The programme involves a new approach to river flood protection: the widening of river beds rather than the construction of dykes or levees. Measures were taken at 30 different locations in the Netherlands. The programme was initiated after two major flooding events in the 1990s. This led to an urgency to act within the Dutch government, in order to protect its citizens from future flooding events.

The ‘system’ is geographically defined as the main branches of the rivers Maas and Rhine, spanning from the Dutch border to where the sea dominates. The measures taken within the programme apply to the winter riverbeds. The Scorecard was filled in by one of the project developers, part of the national government. In what follows, we will go over each of the transformational adaptation domains and provide justifications of the solution’s scores on each of the characteristics.

Figure B-3: Locations where river-widening measures are being taken (red dots)

Scope

The adaptation project affects the entire river system, i.e., the main branches of the rivers Maas and Rhine. Through the project, not only the winter riverbeds where the measures are being taken are protected. It also aims to protect the entire hinterland, the areas beyond the dykes. With this, the effects of the programme extend to the entire polder landscape which the Netherlands is. The adaptation programme is initiated by the national government but it involves all layers of government, including local and provincial governments. The funding also comes from various sources. The programme is mainly funded with national budgets, but the nature/ecological or recreational component which are part of the project are funded regionally. The project takes place in both the public and the private domain in the sense that the rivers themselves are public domain but on the winter riverbeds there are more around 10,000 private owners (e.g., farmers). To widen the rivers, these owners had to be expropriated.

The programme could potentially be expanded to a larger area within the Netherlands, but there is greater potential for it to be replicated elsewhere. The programme’s approach can be applied to all lowland river areas in Europe. There is broad public outreach about the programme, encouraging its replication throughout Europe. As mentioned in the introduction, it is one of the most cited adaptation programmes in literature and has received several prizes for its groundbreaking and integrative approach.

Impacts

The project raises awareness on climate change among the public. At the national level, the goal was set to move from dyke construction to creating more room for rivers. The government actively communicates why this approach is necessary in the face of climate change and its benefit over more traditional grey infrastructure-based approaches. The impact of this widening of the rivers was thoroughly calculated and assessed beforehand to demonstrate that this new approach does not entail any new risks. On the contrary, it ensures a lot more safety. Demonstrating that this nature-

based approach is a viable alternative to traditional flood protection measures enhances its acceptance.

All decisions concerning the adaptation programme were made by a large group of decisionmakers, involving people from different levels of government and with different types of expertise. It has led to new forms of cooperation in the sense that the programme was nationally initiated but the implementation happens at a more local level. Locally implemented measures enhance the safety of upstream neighbours. Therefore, the project has a large solidarity-related component to it. Local authorities can benefit themselves, mostly from the nature or recreational value created by the measures. Especially in the implementation phase at the local level, citizen participation was key. As is common practice in the Netherlands, these local measures were shaped through multiple consultation rounds. The Room for the River programme has resulted in the widening of rivers becoming an integral part of national policy.

Depth

The project involved large-scale depoldering, leading to the creation of nature zones. In Nijmegen, for example, a large bypass was constructed in an area which was previously dominated by indoor horticulture. We can therefore speak of a significant shift in (economic) focus in some parts of the affected river system. The adaptation programme involves a large infrastructural change and an approach which was previously not used in the area. More so, this large-scale widening of rivers as an alternative to dykes is internationally recognised as an innovative approach.

The project was initiated as an urgent response to several flood events in the 1990s. The probability of high waters has increased and the rivers no longer had sufficient capacity to deal with these high waters. The root cause of these high waters is climate change which has led to an increase in precipitation, snowmelt and runoff in other countries outside of the Netherlands. This water travels through the river system to the Netherlands, leading to flood events. This root cause can, obviously, not be addressed with the adaptation programme. What can be addressed is the capacity of rivers.

Temporality

The widening of rivers has become an integral part of the Dutch national flood protection strategy and there is no intention to go back to traditional grey infrastructure-based approaches. After its ending in 2015, a follow-up programme Room for the River 2.0 was introduced to shape the long-term vision of the Dutch river management. Rather than being driven by an urgent need to respond to floods, this programme has a much more long-term focus. Analyses are done of what the Netherlands will look like at the end of the century and how strong the system should be to withstand future shocks, not only considering floods but also increasingly extreme droughts. This programme also pays more attention to the win-win-win aspect of widening rivers: increased protection from extreme weather, increased nature value and increased recreative value. Despite the goal of widening rivers as an alternative to dykes, there are also opponents to widening rivers as this requires more space and is more costly. The follow-up programme therefore has to justify the higher expenses associated with river widening, based on the value it adds (e.g., in terms of ecosystem services). Not only the initial implementation of measures is costly, also the maintenance is quite costly. Nature development, for example, requires adequate pruning while also giving vegetation the room to flourish and expand.

Although the follow-up projects allows for the introduction of new measures, once the large infrastructural works to rivers are done there is little flexibility to adjust to new issues as they arise. For example, within the initial Room for the River project the focus was only on flood protection. As droughts become more of an issue, there is little room to make adjustments to the original measures.

Inclusivity

As mentioned, the adaptation programme required the relocation of thousands of citizens. Citizens were either expropriated and/or their houses were moved. All citizens, vulnerable or non-vulnerable, were treated equally in this regard. Decisionmakers tried to affect as few citizens as possible by such measures. Because of the programme's large scale, special attention could not be paid to (economically) vulnerable groups. Everyone was, however, offered adequate compensation for their homes so one group of the population was not (dis)advantaged more than other groups.

Through the widening of rivers rather than installing dykes, additional natural spaces were created, indirectly leading to a reduction (capturing) of CO2 emissions. This was, however, not an intended goal of the programme. To implement the programme, soil was transferred from measures which required the removal of soil to closely located places which required additional soil in order to keep a soil balance. This contributed to the sustainable use of natural resources. Moreover, biodiversity is increased through the programme, both on land and in the rivers.

Because the programme's large scale it has created employment opportunities for many people (indirect consequence of the programme, not a goal). Moreover, courses were organised to educate people on their approach to river management leading to an educational value. Through flood protection, the programme largely contributes to the health and wellbeing of people living near the rivers.

Results

Figure B-4: TransformAR Scorecard results dashboard for the Room for the River case study

The general assessment of this case study is positive. It is a large-scale programme, affecting a large geographic area and thousands of citizens. The programme is considered a 'best practice' in the field of river management and climate adaptation, leading to broad public outreach and high replicability. The programme involves many levels of governance and different financing channels, as well as engagement from citizens. The only suggestions for improvement which can be made are: 1) an explicit consideration of vulnerable groups. This could happen through an assessment of, for example, the impact of the programme on the relocation of (economically) vulnerable citizens and attempting to disproportionately benefit this group. 2) Some form of flexibility could be built in, such that infrastructural works can be adjusted to newly arising (weather) risks, although this is challenging due

to the nature of the project (small-scale digital projects are, for example, much easier to adjust than large-scale infrastructural projects). Lastly, 3) the nature component could be a more integral part of the approach. There is huge potential for this project to not only adapt to climate change, but also to mitigate climate change. By replacing grey infrastructure with green infrastructure, areas are not only made more resilient to climate change, this vegetation also captures large amounts of CO₂. These emission reductions can also be used to make a (business) case for widening rivers as opposed to building dykes. The Room for the River 2.0 project already pays more attention to this nature value.

C. Scorecard results for TransformAr partners

Amálie site – Prague, Czech Republic

The Amálie site is a pilot projects of the ČZU, in which experts are implementing specific measures to increase the adaptation of an area of approximately 500 hectares of agricultural land. Measures are being implemented, in particular to retain surface water, plant new alleys of trees, restore natural wetlands, secure erosion-prone slopes, modify cropping practices or monitor the hydrological regime¹².

Mussel raft monitoring – Galicia, Spain

This is one of three solutions in the TransformAr Galicia demonstrator. Mussel raft monitoring: the collection of extensive real-time data from mussel rafts on environmental conditions and production

¹²<https://cvpk.czu.cz/en/r-17791-smart-landscape/r-17792-educational-trail-amalie/r-17793-amalie-nature-trail>

to optimise the management of mussel production in response to climate-related challenges.

Smart Climate Solutions - Egaleo, Greece

The adaptation solution implemented in Egaleo is the provision of real-time weather and air quality data through a Citizen App. The solution also aims to engage with students, who can participate in hackathons where the data is analysed.

Climate change impacts are here and now. The impacts on people, prosperity and planet are already pervasive but unevenly distributed, as stated in the new EU Blueprint strategy (European Commission-EC, 2019). To reduce climate-related risks, the EC and the IPCC agree that transformational adaptation is essential. The TransformAr project aims to develop and demonstrate products and services to launch and accelerate large-scale and disruptive adaptive process for transformational adaptation in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe.

The 6 TransformAr lighthouse demonstrators face a common challenge: water-related risks and impacts of climate change. Based on existing successful initiatives, the project will develop, test and demonstrate solutions and pathways, integrated in Innovation Packages, in 6 territories.

Transformational pathways, including an integrated risk assessment approach are co-developed by means of 9 Transformational Adaptive Blocks. A set of 22 tested actionable adaptive solutions are tested and demonstrated, ranging from nature-based solutions, innovative technologies, financing, insurance and governance models, awareness and behavioral change solutions.

TransformAr

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